

Conference Materials

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Performance Evaluation of Feed Opening Section Based on Throughput Metrics

Abstract

Introduction This study presents the development, fabrication, and experimental evaluation of four 3D-printed hopper prototypes (FOS – Feed Opening Section) designed for use in polymer extrusion systems. The goal was to create functionally consistent hoppers with different shape of feed opening that could be assess the flow characteristics and throughput efficiency of various hopper geometries under controlled test conditions.

Hopper Design and 3D Printing of Functional Prototypes All hoppers were designed with a uniform hopper height of 450 mm and a wall angle of 70°. A consistent feed opening diameter of 45 mm was used across all models. To fit within the printer maximum height, the hopper height was reduced to 335 mm.

Polycarbonate (PC) filament was selected as the model material, and SR-100 was used as the support material due to geometric complexity. After printing, the inner surfaces of each hopper were smoothed to achieve uniform surface roughness, ensuring performance during material flow.

Throughput Testing of Hopper Models Comparative throughput studies were conducted using granulated pellets of sizes 2×3 mm, 3×3 mm, and 5×3 mm. For each test, 3 kg of pellets were discharged through the hopper outlet. Each pellet size was tested ten times per model.

Results Table 1 summarizes the throughput rates for each model across different pellet sizes.

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Table 1

Pellet size, mm	Throughput of the FOS models, kg/h			
	FOS 1	FOS 2	FOS 3	FOS 4
2×3	6923 ±35	4648 ±20	3948 ±25	4473 ±25
3×3	6207 ±35	4372 ±20	3633 ±25	4120 ±25
5×3	6626 ±35	4569 ±20	3830 ±25	4450 ±25

Graph 1 shows FOS 1 consistently exhibited the highest throughput, attributed to its larger feed opening. Among the remaining hoppers, FOS 2 demonstrated superior throughput due to its geometry being most similar to FOS 1.

Graph 1 Throughput of the FOS models, kg/h

Conclusion

This work demonstrates the effectiveness of using 3D printing to quickly prototype and evaluate different hopper geometries for granular material flow. The methodology enabled controlled testing of discharge rates and showed how subtle geometric differences can significantly impact performance. The approach used in this study offers a practical framework for preliminary testing of bulk material handling systems using additive manufacturing technologies.

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